

One of the **easiest strategies** to implement for attracting partners and clients is **advertising**. **Ad campaigns** for serious games tend to be **slightly different** than adverts in other niches, which should always be taken into consideration when coming up with a marketing plan.

Here are some things that one should have in mind when advertising educational products.

#1 Choose The Right Ad Networks

* **Google Ads** (previously known as Adwords) are the **perfect way of reaching people** that are searching for serious games or researching the topic. Use them to **target keywords and phrases** that are related to your educational platform – this way you can be sure that the ads will be seen only by people that may be interested in serious game products.

* **Facebook Ads** offer a whole different approach to advertising. FB Ads use its own **deep demographic** and **psychographic** data pool to reach relevant users of your choosing. Think about the **job position, age, and interests** of the person that might be interested in serious game products and let FB Ads do the job!

#2 Create Relevant Ad Creatives

Each of the advertising networks above requires a different approach to presenting your message. **Google Ads are intent-based**, meaning that they will mostly bring users that are actively looking for serious game-related things. **Facebook Ads** are shown to all people that **match chosen targeting criteria**.

#3 Monitor And Optimize

Don't simply "fire and forget" your campaigns.

You should **keep track of the analytics** to make sure that the ads are reaching relevant people and that they're bringing traffic to your website.